

C# DA FAYLLAR ORQALI MA'LUMOTLARNI SARALASH VA FAYLLAR BILAN ISHLASH ALGORITMLARINING XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Algoritmning amaliy ahamiyati, jihatlari, va c# da fayllar bilan hosil qilish haqida so'z yuritiladi. Hamda fayllarning algoritmlari oilasiga mansub bo'lgan alogoritmlari va ularning yaratilish asoslari ishlab chiqish asoslari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek fayllarning algoritmlarining strukturasi hamda umumiy mohiyati o'rganilgan

Abstract: The practical importance of the algorithm, aspects, and generation with files in C# are discussed. Algorithms belonging to the family of algorithms of files and the basics of their creation were analyzed. Also, the structure and general essence of algorithms of files were studied.

Kalit so'zlar: Fayllar orqali Tasodifiy sonlar generatori, oqimli shifrlar, File 1. Kodni fayllar sistemasida biror nom bilan saqlash lozim (hello.cs)

Kommandalar satrida `csc /debug hello.cs` buyrug'ini bajarish lozim Ushbu buyrug' bajarilgach, natijaviy .exe kengaytmali fayl hosil bo'ladi. Agar kompilyatsiya jarayonida xatolik yuzaga kelsa, ma'lumot chiqariladi. /debug parametri bajariluvchi faylga maxsus simvollarni joylashtiradi. Natijada exe faylni qayta ishlovchi dasturda taxlil qilinayotganda stekni kuzatib borishlari mumkin. 3. Dasturni ishlatish natijasida, ekranga Hello yozuvi chiqariladi. C# dasturlash tilida Console rejimda dastur tuzish uchun yangi loyiha yaratamiz (File/New Project/Visual C#/ Console Application). Ushbu loyihamiz- ning nomini masalan "1-misol" deb nomlaymiz. Bizga C# kodini yozish uchun yangi oyna ochiladi. Console rejimida ishlash uchun .NET da Console sinfi ishlatiladi. Bu sinfnig afzalligi 2 ta qismdan iborat bo'lib: uning barcha metodlari o'zgarmas, sanoqli bo'lib, uni ishlatish uchun nusxalash shart emas. U kiritish, chiqarish va xatoliklarni chiqarishni o'z ichiga oladi. Odatda kiritish, chiqarish standart Console-da amalga oshiriladi (agar u bo'lmasa, masalan oynali masalalarda chiqarish amalga oshirilmaydi), lekin kiritish va chiqarish oqimlarini o'zgartirish mumkin. Console bilan ishlashda asosan 4 metod ishlatiladi: Read, ReadLine, Write, WriteLine, birinchi ikkitasi kiritish, qolgani chiqarish metodlari hisoblanadi. Read metodi. Read metodi kiritish qurilmalaridan belgini qabul qiladi. U int tipida kiritilgan belgi kodini qaytaradi va hech narsa kiritilmagan bo'lsa, -1 ni qaytaradi. Masalan: `int i = Console.Read(); Console.WriteLine(i);`

Bu dastur kiritilgan belgi kodini ekranga chiqarib beradi.

ReadLine metodi. ReadLine metodi kiritish qurilmalaridan matnning satrini qabul qiladi (uning qiymati keyingi satrga o‘tish belgisi bilan tugaydi). U string tipidagi qiymat yoki null (agar kiritish amalga oshmagan bo‘lsa) qiymatini qaytaradi. Masalan: `string s = Console.ReadLine(); Console.WriteLine("Kiritilgan satr : " + s);` Write va WriteLine metodlari. Write metodi unga yuborilgan o‘zgaruvchi qiymatini ekranga chiqarish vazifasini bajaradi. U string tipini qabul qiladi. U barcha bazali tiplar uchun ishlaydi.

1-rasm Local Databas1.

Shuning uchun uni parametr sifatida chaqirish mumkin. `Console.WriteLine(1);`
`Console.WriteLine(0.75)`

```
using System; namespace _01_misol
{ class Program { static void Main(string[] args)
{
Console.WriteLine("1-misol");
Console.ReadKey(); }
}
}
```


2-rasm Local Databasga yangi Item qo‘shish.

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